

Excitation of Bulk Shear Waves in Steel by Magnetostrictive Coupling

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Abstract – This work presents a novel configuration of an EMAT that, through magnetostriction, generates shear waves propagating normal to the surface of a steel sample. The transduction mechanism of the EMAT is discussed, and the effects of altering parameters of the EMAT are illustrated. If the EMAT is set up correctly, then it is shown that the EMAT provides means for ultrasonically measuring the magnetostriction of a sample.

INTRODUCTION

This work demonstrates a new configuration of an electromagnetic acoustic transducer (EMAT) that magnetostrictively generates bulk shear waves in steel. Magnetostriction is the phenomenon of a ferromagnetic material changing shape when it becomes magnetized, and previous studies by R. B. Thompson [1–2] showed that magnetostrictive coupling of EMATs with steel could be used to excite shear horizontal (SH) plate waves. In that case, EMATs with serpentine-shaped meander coils were used; however, here it is shown that, by changing the configuration of the coil, one can generate shear waves that propagate normal to the sample surface.

EMAT CONFIGURATION

The new EMAT configuration is shown in Figure 1. It consists of an apertured spiral racetrack coil placed on a steel sample with a static magnetic field H_0 applied tangentially to the sample surface. An ac current in the coil creates an oscillating magnetic

Figure 1. EMAT configuration that magnetostrictively generates bulk shear waves.

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field H_0 , and the copper mask shields the sample from this field except in the middle.

We propose that bulk shear waves are excited through a magnetostrictive transduction mechanism that is similar to Thompson's model of the way that shear horizontal plate waves are launched by meander coil EMATs. The gist of the proposed mechanism at work here is summarized at the bottom of Figure 1. Static magnetic field H_0 introduces tension (or compression) into the sample due to magnetostriction. Oscillating magnetic field H_0 rotates magnetization near the surface of the sample, and this rotates axes of tension underneath each half of the coil, which, in turn, creates shear stresses. For example, if the dashed rectangles in the figure represent near-surface zones of tension underneath the halves of the coil due to H_0 alone, then they are distorted into the solid parallelograms by the oscillating field H_0 . The near-surface shear forces f then generate bulk shear waves that propagate into the sample.

Even from this simplified picture, one can make several verifiable observations about the transducer. First, the dominant shear wave is generated at the center of the coil, and it is polarized parallel to the field H_0 . Both halves of the coil contribute shear forces f_y that excite this wave. Secondly, shear waves are generated at the side edges of the coil that are oppositely polarized as the central wave. Finally, since shear forces f_x on one half of the coil are opposed by their counterparts on the other half of the coil, not much shear wave polarized orthogonal to H_0 is generated, especially when the halves are not separated by much space in the center of the coil.

Figure 2. Experimental setup for measuring the amplitude of bulk shear waves.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUE

The generation efficiency of this EMAT configuration was measured as a function of static magnetic field H_0 in the setup shown in Figure 2. A 5.3 cm x 2.4 cm EMAT coil containing nine turns was taped to a 254 μm thick Cu mask with a 6 cm^2 aperture. The masked EMAT was placed on a mechanically- and chemically-polished surface of a 12.7 cm x 6.4 cm x 1.2 cm plate of cold-rolled low-carbon (1018) steel, and good electrical contact between the Cu mask and the sample was ensured.

Static magnetic field H_0 was provided by an electromagnet. A gated amplifier issued pulses consisting of three or four cycles of sinusoids at 791 kHz, and the amplifier output was adjusted continuously to maintain a constant peak EMAT current of 5 A. The amplitude of the pulse directly transmitted to the other side of the sample was recorded by a 1.2 cm diameter piezoelectric transducer that was mounted on the bottom of the sample, centered underneath the EMAT coil, and polarized parallel to field H_0 .

We varied the orientation and dimensions of the EMAT coil to investigate the sensitivities of the generation efficiency to these factors. For additional comparison purposes, we measured the efficiency of a meander coil that magnetostrictively generates surface-skimming SH waves (using a setup reported earlier [3]). To determine whether Lorentz forces contribute to the generation transduction of the new EMAT configuration, we also attempted to excite bulk shear waves in a 2.5 cm thick plate of Al.

Figure 3. Normalized amplitudes of bulk shear waves generated by the new EMAT configuration (O) and SH waves generated by a meander coil EMAT (\diamond).

The B-H curve and transverse incremental permeability of the steel specimen were measured, and a crude strain gage measurement of the magnetostriction was attempted. Details of these measurement techniques were provided in a previous work [4].

GENERATION EFFICIENCY

The transduction efficiency of the new EMAT configuration as a function of the static magnetic field H_0 is plotted in Figure 3 ("bulk shear wave" data), and it is seen to behave similarly as the efficiency of a meander coil EMAT that generates surface-skimming SH waves. (Both curves are normalized with respect to their maximum values.) This result provides evidence that the transduction mechanisms of the two EMATs are similar, which suggests that the model of magnetostrictive transduction proposed above for the new EMAT configuration is valid to first approximation.

In the Al sample, we find that the new EMAT configuration generates negligible bulk shear waves. The implication for steel samples, then, is that Lorentz forces do not contribute much to the transduction mechanism, and that shear waves are generated largely by magnetostriction.

The effect of rotating the EMAT and mask by 90° with respect to field H_0 is shown in Figure 4. Among the most apparent differences between the two orientations of the EMAT is the fact that the generation efficiency for one orientation drops off at a point where the efficiency for the other remains high.

Figure 4. Normalized amplitudes of bulk shear waves generated by the original EMAT configuration (dashed line), by a coil rotated 90° (Δ), and by a large coil with an open center (\square).

These differences assuredly stem from the different relative angles between H_0 and H_ω ; the generation efficiency of meander coil EMATs changes similarly when H_ω is parallel rather than perpendicular to H_0 (in which case, Lamb waves, rather than SH plate waves, are generated [1,2]).

When a larger coil (7.4 cm x 6.1 cm) with an open center (3.7 cm x 2.5 cm clearance) is used (with the long dimension oriented parallel to H_0), the generation efficiency appears to be a superposition of the rotated and unrotated cases of the original EMAT coil (see Figure 4). We speculate that, in the case of the large EMAT coil, there is a significant amount of stray eddy current in the sample that runs perpendicular to the field H_0 and contributes unintentional fields H_ω that are oriented parallel to H_0 .

MEASUREMENT OF MAGNETOSTRICTION

Since the efficiencies of the new EMAT configuration and the meander coil EMAT behave similarly (see Figure 3), one can use Thompson's modeling of the meander coil EMAT to obtain a first order approximation of the relationship between the amplitude of the bulk shear waves and magnetostriction. It recently has been shown [3] that, near saturation fields H_0 , the amplitude Ψ of SH waves generated magnetostrictively by a meander coil EMAT obeys the relationship,

$$|\lambda| \propto \Psi \sqrt{\mu_t} \frac{\left(\frac{B_0 + \mu_t H_\omega}{\mu_t H_\omega} + \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right)^2}{\left| \frac{B_0 - \mu_t H_\omega}{\mu_t H_\omega} - \frac{\mu_t H_\omega}{B_0} \right|},$$

where μ_t is the transverse incremental permeability, B_0 is the magnetic induction due to H_0 and λ is the magnetostriction coefficient (the longitudinal strain due to H_0). As a first estimate, we assume that a similar relationship holds for bulk shear waves that are excited by our EMAT.

Substituting measurements of the bulk shear wave amplitude from Figure 3 and measurements of the transverse incremental permeability μ_t and induction B_0 into this result, and estimating $H_\omega \cong 1.5$ kA/m for 5 A of peak current, we derive the estimate of the magnetostriction shown in Figure 5. It should be noted that this result is an estimate of the near-surface

magnetostriction of the steel, because it is derived from the efficiency of the transduction processes, which are confined to the skin depth of the sample (the depth of penetration of field H_0).

Crude strain gage measurements of magnetostriction coefficient λ confirm that the maximum magnetostriction occurs at 7 – 8 kA/m. The shape of the magnetostriction curve suggests that the top of the sample is under slight compression [5], which might be due to flexure of the sample as a result of magnetic attraction between the sample and the pole pieces of the electromagnet.

CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates that bulk shear waves can be generated magnetostrictively in steel using a new EMAT configuration. The generation efficiency of the EMAT compares with that of a meander coil EMAT that generates surface-skimming SH waves, hence, indicating that the magnetostrictive transduction mechanisms of the two EMATs are similar. Using Thompson's model of the transduction mechanism of meander coil EMATs as a springboard, we propose a simple model of the way that the new EMAT configuration magnetostrictively launches bulk shear waves.

The transduction efficiency is shown to be sensitive to the orientation and dimensions of the EMAT coil. If the coil is set up correctly, then preliminary tests show that EMAT-generated bulk shear waves may be used to measure magnetostriction. Such measurements might prove to be advantageous in instances where it would not be

Figure 5. Estimate of λ derived from measurements of bulk shear waves that are excited by the new EMAT configuration.

feasible to use strain gages (for example, on hot plates) or where it would be desirable to focus on the near-surface magnetostriction of a sample (for example, to assess the extent of irradiation-induced damage near the inner surface of steel reactor pressure vessels).

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